

FLAME NEWSLETTER – ISSUE 5

National Observatory of Athens

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FLAME is a research project carried out at the Institute for Environmental Research and Sustainable Development (IERSD) of the National Observatory of Athens (NOA). The overarching goal of the project is the study and characterization of the environmental conditions that promote extreme wildfires in Greece, intending to increase awareness and enhance the preparedness of fire operatives and the public.

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Editorial

Welcome to **Issue 5** of FLAME's e-Newsletter!

During the period from December 2022 to June 2023, we continued advancing fire weather research in Greece and Europe. After publishing the first handbook on synoptic-scale pyrometeorology (refer to the previous issue of our newsletter), we submitted the related work for publication (currently under review) to the Agricultural and Forest Meteorology journal. We have also concluded a prototype pan-European analysis of fire weather extremes and submitted the related work for publication (currently under review) to the Agricultural and Forest Meteorology journal. Whilst the 2022 fire season in Greece was relatively quiet, our team continued to devote effort to increasing public awareness of fire weather in Greece by monitoring fire weather conditions and regularly issuing fire weather outlooks and warnings. Last but not least, we released FLAME's third promotional video, debating on what we should do and not do to address the problem of extreme wildfires.

Enjoy reading!

Theodore M. Giannaros
Principal Investigator of FLAME
IERSD/NOA
26.06.2023

THE TOP 10 MOST EXTREME WILDFIRES IN GREECE

An analysis of satellite-derived data on burned areas and fire growth rates from the FIRE-D dataset, covering the period from 2003 to 2022 in Greece, has revealed interesting findings regarding the most extreme wildfires of the past two decades in Greece (see image below).

By utilizing the daily growth rate, we have identified the ten most extreme wildfire events based on the sheer extent of area burned within a single day. The key findings of this analysis can be summarized as follows:

1. The ten most extreme wildfires collectively burned more than 280,000 hectares.
2. All ten extreme events exhibited exceptionally large daily growth rates surpassing 7,500 hectares per day.
3. The catastrophic wildfire in Arcadia during August 2007 stands out as having the highest daily growth rate, exceeding 25,000 hectares within a single day.
4. The most recent devastating wildfire in Euboea, which occurred in August 2021, ranks fourth with a maximum daily growth rate surpassing 15,000 hectares per day.
5. Out of the ten extreme wildfires, six occurred in the Peloponnese.
6. Interestingly, six out of the ten extreme wildfires occurred during the same fire season in 2007.

Οι 10 πιο ακραίες πυρκαγιές στην Ελλάδα

The above findings strongly emphasize the urgent need for implementing integrated management strategies to tackle the issue of extreme wildfires, leveraging cutting-edge scientific knowledge. In this regard, the METEO Unit of NOAA unit offers the following solutions, supported through the FLAME research project:

- Monitoring of fire weather conditions, including the flammability assessment of dead fine fuels, utilizing Greece's densest network of automatic weather stations (currently comprising over 500 stations).
- Daily forecasts of fire danger based on the Canadian Forest Fire Weather Index System (CFFWIS), properly adapted to Greece's fire environment.
- On-demand prediction of fire spread and behavior, utilizing the IRIS 2.0 rapid response fire spread forecasting system.
- On-demand fire analysis of active wildfires.

By exploiting these advanced tools and resources, we can proactively address the challenges posed by extreme wildfires and work towards more effective mitigation and response strategies.

The following video summarizes many of these services while highlighting that unless we break down the silos that currently keep operational and research agencies isolated, it will be impossible to achieve adaptation and enhanced preparedness for the new reality of extreme wildfires.

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=s36YvSjfMo>

PRELIMINARY ASSESSMENT OF CANADIAN WILDFIRES (MAY – JUNE 2023)

In May 2023, a persistent upper-tropospheric blocking system developed over Western Canada (see image below), leading to abnormally hot and dry weather conditions. This, in turn, resulted in the development of extreme fire weather conditions across Saskatchewan and Alberta, fueling multiple wildfires.

Throughout the latter half of May, extreme surface fire weather conditions occasionally coincided with enhanced winds or atmospheric instability caused by changes in upper-tropospheric conditions, such as approaching short-wave troughs and cold fronts. These changes in the upper atmosphere brought about transient periods of extreme fire weather conditions and significant shifts in fire behavior. Some wildfires were driven by hot, dry, and windy conditions, while others were influenced by pyroconvection, resulting in plume-driven fire behavior.

The combination of these extreme fire weather conditions and prevailing drought conditions played a crucial role in the development of erratic fire behavior and rapid fire spread across

multiple wildfires. As a result, numerous evacuations were ordered along the fire perimeters in Alberta and Saskatchewan.

These synoptic-scale fire weather conditions persisted into the first half of June, with the blocking system shifting eastwards towards Central/Eastern Canada. Consequently, extreme fire weather conditions emerged predominantly in Quebec, sparking another series of intense wildfires in the region. Meanwhile, the fire fronts in Alberta and parts of British Columbia remained active with periodic episodes of extreme behavior.

The new wave of wildfire activity in Quebec primarily originated from lightning strikes (see image below), igniting fires across the southern areas of the province shortly after the passage of a short-wave trough, which triggered significant convective activity in an already dry environment. The outbreak of these extreme wildfires in Quebec, combined with a low-pressure system over Southeast Canada and Northeast USA, resulted in the transport of thick smoke, significantly impacting air quality in the affected regions.

Notably, satellite retrievals indicate that the onset of the 2023 fire season in Canada is the most severe in the past 22 years.

FLAME PUBLICITY FACTS

Publications in peer-reviewed scientific journals

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Conference posters and presentations

Papavasileiou G, Giannaros TM (2023) Synoptic-scale fire weather forecasting in Greece. 2nd MeteoXchange ECS Conference, Online, 13 – 14 April 2023.

FLAME in the media

<https://www.protothema.gr/greece/article/1353033/meteo-oi-10-pio-akraies-dasikes-purkagies-stin-ellada-apo-to-2003-ekapsan-28-ekat-stremmata/>

<https://www.kathimerini.gr/life/environment/562276063/case-study-to-mati-gia-tin-apofygineas-tragodias/>

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